

ISic2721

I.Sicily inscription 2721

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble (white)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museum or catacomb Antiquarium

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

0. [---]

1. [---έτελεύ]τησ[εν---]

2. [---] τῆ ἡρ(ὸ) [---]

2a. []

Apparatus

Text after Griesheimer 1996 (line numbering amended)

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645141

PHI 333388

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum*

graecum. At 46.1292

Griesheimer, M. 1996. Nouvelles inscriptions funéraires de la catacombe Saint-Jean. *Rivista di Archeologia Cristiana*. 72: 115-132. At 127 no.12 fig.12

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